

THE CONDUCTOMETRIC METHOD OF DETERMINING THE SOLUBLE SALT CONTENT OF SOILS FOR USE IN SOIL SURVEY WORK.

BY R. C. HOON, J. K. MALHOTRA, AND LAKSHMI CHAND JAIN.

The conductivity of soil suspensions has been determined with Dionic water tester. The salt content of soils may be derived from the conductivity of 1 : 15 soil suspensions by a very simple relationship, i.e., the conductivity value, if divided by one thousand, gives the percentage salt content of soils.

To determine the total salt content of soils by the present method, the use of distilled water only for making the soil suspensions is suggested as it has been shown that the use of salt-containing water brings about depression in the conductivity value which varies with the nature of the salts present in the water used.

This conductometric method of determining soluble salt content has been tested for a set of soils derived from the various parts of India and the results seem to justify the adoption of this method in this country for soil survey work.

The importance of soil survey work is now well recognised. The classification of soils for project or land reclamation work is mostly based on the p_u values of soils and their soluble salt content. During recent years fairly robust p_u meters have been evolved for field work.

As early as 1897 Whitney and Mean (*U. S. Dept. Agr. Div. Soil Bull.*, No. 8) suggested the use of a quick electrolytic method for the determination of salt content of soils. The work of Briggs (*U. S. Dept. Agr. Div. Soil Bull.*, 1899, No. 15), Davis and Bryan (*U. S. Dept. Agr. Exp. Sta. Rec.*, 1911, 24, 2107), Davis (*U. S. Dept. Agr.*, 1927, Circ. No. 423) and several others helped considerably to refine the conductometric method. In the present time number of portable types of instruments are available for use by the worker engaged on the survey of soils for purposes of land utilisation or reclamation.

The earlier advocates of the conductometric method determined the electrical conductivity of extracts prepared by centrifuging the soil suspensions. Joseph and Martin (*J. Agric. Sci.*, 1923, 13, 49) measured the specific conductivities of soil extracts at 30° and obtained the percentage salt content by comparing with the specific resistance of a solution containing 1% of sodium chloride and sulphate. Atkins (*ibid.*, 1924, 14, 198) determined the specific conductivities of soil extracts at 0°. More recently, however, Sen and Wright (*ibid.*, 1931, 21, 1), Sen (*ibid.*,

1932, 22, 212) and Dutoit and Perold (*Soil Sci.*, 1935, 39, 59), and others measured the specific conductivities of aqueous suspensions at 25°.

Most of the field workers in conductometric work had used 1:5 soil-water ratio for preparing soil extracts or suspensions. It was considered of interest to determine the conductivity of soil suspensions at different soil-water ratios and to see which ratio afforded values of salt content of soils that agreed most with those obtained gravimetrically.

In the present work measurement of conductivities of soil suspensions was done with Dionic water tester. As the electrode system of this apparatus is graduated for use at temperatures between 10° and 40°, no temperature control was found necessary. The gravimetric determination was done by evaporating an aliquot part of soil extracts prepared from 1:5 soil suspensions.

Effect of Dilution of Soil Suspension on its Conductivity.

The effect of dilution of soil suspension on conductivity was studied for a number of soils at dilutions ranging from 1:5 to 1:150 soil-water ratios. The results are plotted in Fig. 1 and bring out the usual parabolic relationship analogous to that obtained with not very dilute solutions of salts. It was thus indicated that for this type of work it would be better to stick to some one convenient dilution of the soil suspension and to obtain the most suitable relationship for conductivity: soluble salt for that particular soil-water ratio by examining a number of soils of varying salt contents.

FIG. 1.

The Relationship of Salt content of Soils and Conductivity of Soil suspensions at varying Soil-water Ratios.

(a) 1:5 Soil-water Suspensions.—This concentration of the soil suspension is considered very convenient in soil work. For the gravimetric estimation of the salt content the soil extracts are usually prepared from suspensions of this strength. For the present work the 1:5 soil suspensions were shaken for a few hours and their conductivities were then determined with the Dionic water tester in the usual way. The suspensions were then extracted through porous candles and the salt content of the soil extracts determined gravimetrically. A large number of soils were thus examined. The results of soluble salt content of soils determined gravimetrically (*S*) and the conductivities of soil suspensions (*C*) on plotting indicated an almost linear relationship as long as the conductivities did not exceed 400. A statistical examination of the results yielded the following relationship:—

$$10^3 S = 0.314C + 25.4 \quad \dots (i)$$

It is thus clear that for soils having a conductivity of their 1:5 soil suspensions greater than 400, a wider soil-water ratio is to be adopted.

(b) 1:30 & 1:50 Soil-water Suspensions.—Over 300 soil samples with percentage salt contents varying from 0.1 to 2.0% were taken and the conductivities of their 1:30 and 1:50 soil suspensions determined as before. By computing the salt content of these soils from the conductivities of their 1:30 and 1:50 soil suspensions by formula (i) it was found that the results obtained were comparatively high than the directly determined values. That might be expected as the conductivity : dilution relationship is not linear. The conductivities of 1:30 and 1:50 soil suspensions (*C*) were statistically examined in relation to the directly determined percentage salt content of soils (*S*) on lines similar to those adopted for obtaining formula (i) and the following two relationships were thus obtained:—

$$\text{For 1:30 soil suspensions: } 10^2 S = 0.17C - 2.8 \quad \dots (ii)$$

$$\text{For 1:50 soil suspensions: } 10^2 S = 0.26C - 0.8 \quad \dots (iii)$$

The results of percentage salt content obtained from the conductivities of soil suspensions at the three dilutions on the basis of the formulae (i)-(iii) for a few soils are given in Table I. A comparison of the results show that the salt contents obtained on the basis of formula (ii) afford a better agreement to the directly determined salt content values than those

TABLE I.

No.	Reg. No.	Soluble salt content from conductivity of				No.	Reg. No.	Soluble salt content from conductivity of			
		Direct.	1:5 soil suspension by (f).	1:50 soil suspension by (ff).	1:50 soil suspension by (fff).			Direct.	1:5 soil suspension by (f).	1:50 soil suspension by (ff).	1:50 soil suspension by (fff).
1	3453	0.12%	0.21%	0.16%	0.24%	30	3374	0.42%	0.48%	0.58%	0.43%
2	2903	0.14	0.18	0.18	0.24	31	3338	0.45	0.45	0.55	0.58
3	2894	0.14	0.14	0.18	0.25	32	3004	0.47	0.41	0.41	0.47
4	3002	0.15	0.16	0.18	0.25	33	3468	0.47	0.57	0.48	0.54
5	3009	0.15	0.18	0.18	0.23	34	3330	0.50	0.52	0.55	0.54
6	3204	0.16	0.17	0.15	0.20	35	3302	0.53	0.46	0.57	0.50
7	3205	0.16	0.17	0.22	0.23	36	3287	0.55	0.46	0.52	0.49
8	3017	0.16	0.22	0.23	0.33	37	2985	0.59	0.55	0.59	0.59
9	3196	0.17	0.20	0.26	0.28	38	3019	0.61	0.58	0.57	0.56
10	3088	0.17	0.15	0.19	0.21	39	3465	0.65	0.55	0.57	0.64
11	3366	0.17	0.25	0.24	0.30	40	3321	0.67	0.55	0.62	0.64
12	2889	0.17	0.18	0.21	0.30	41	3445	0.69	0.57	0.64	0.65
13	2893	0.17	0.16	0.21	0.25	42	3189	0.73	0.65	0.72	0.71
14	3007	0.18	0.26	0.23	0.25	43	2988	0.74	0.71	0.71	0.68
15	3072	0.18	0.19	0.18	0.23	44	3137	0.77	0.62	0.70	0.75
16	2978	0.20	0.17	0.17	0.20	45	3027	0.79	0.79	0.74	0.85
17	3090	0.20	0.16	0.18	0.21	46	2926	0.81	0.77	0.81	0.82
18	3176	0.20	0.24	0.31	0.38	47	3262	0.85	0.96	0.86	0.88
19	3370	0.21	0.22	0.24	0.29	48	2975	0.88	0.92	0.89	0.90
20	3229	0.23	0.29	0.30	0.40	49	3280	0.92	0.96	0.92	0.90
21	3333	0.25	0.26	0.28	0.34	50	3304	0.96	0.93	0.89	0.90
22	3174	0.27	0.27	0.30	0.37	51	3323	1.01	0.96	0.98	0.93
23	3257	0.29	0.33	0.31	0.36	52	3325	1.14	1.11	1.15	1.24
24	3329	0.31	0.29	0.31	0.43	53	2993	1.15	1.15	1.10	1.12
25	3233	0.32	0.32	0.31	0.40	54	3157	1.22	1.03	1.16	1.23
26	3378	0.35	0.38	0.48	0.49	55	2973	1.37	1.32	1.25	1.29
27	2999	0.38	0.45	0.40	0.43	56	2972	1.47	1.07	1.50	1.55
28	3463	0.40	0.39	0.32	0.41	57	3058	1.80	1.58	1.59	1.42
29	3309	0.40	0.46	0.47	0.54						

calculated on the basis of the other two formulae when the salt content is of a high order.

(c) 1 : 15 Soil-water Suspensions.—During the course of the work it revealed that the conductivities of 1 : 15 soil suspensions divided by one thousand yielded values of total salt content which were almost equal to the values determined gravimetrically, *i.e.*,

$$S = C \times 1000 \quad \dots \text{(iv)}$$

This observation was extremely significant as for 1 : 15 soil suspensions the salt content of soils might be determined from the conductivity values without the use of any complicated formula. To test the point the conductivities of a large number of soils at 1 : 15 dilution of soil suspension were determined. The results of conductivity and total salt content determined gravimetrically are plotted in Fig. 2, from which it is evident that the points lie fairly well along the mean line. The two lines running parallel to the mean line and at a distance equivalent to 0.1% salt content comprise almost all the points up to a salt content of 0.75%. This indicates that up to a conductivity value of 750 the soluble salt content of soils is given by the above relationship subject to a maximum error of 0.1% (the actual error would be less). For soils having conductivity values greater than 750,

$$S = C/1000 + 0.1 \quad \dots \text{(v)}$$

and is subject to a maximum error of 0.2%.

Interpretation of the Results of Soil Analysis for Soil Classification.

For project or land reclamation work the limiting values for soluble salt content and p_s of soils had been fixed as 0.24% and 5.8% respectively for the Punjab soils, *i.e.* soils having salt content and p_s higher than these values are considered deteriorated and requiring reclamation (Mehta, *Punjab Irrigation Inst. Res. Bull.*, 1927, 39, No. 2). A critical examination was therefore made as to how much error was likely to occur about the limiting value of soluble salt content of soils if the latter was determined conductometrically from 1 : 15 soil suspensions. It was found that for this purpose the limiting values of conductivity could be fixed at 150 and 250 as shown in Fig. 2 by lines AA' and BB', *i.e.*, if the conductivity was less than 150 then the salt content would be less than 0.2% and if the conductivity was more than 250 then the salt content would be greater than 0.2%. For

conductivity values in between the two limits at least 5 results out of 7 would be found to give a correct indication of the salt content.

FIG. 2.

Effect of Shaking of Soil Suspensions.—It is necessary to shake the soil suspensions for 2 to 3 hours before determining the conductivities. This is particularly essential for soils with a high salt content. For soils with low salt content, however, the difference caused by shaking the suspensions in conductivity values is not very significant.

The Quality of Water used for making Soil Suspensions for Conductometric Determination of Total Salt.

Replacement of distilled water for tap or well water obtained locally for making soil suspensions in soil survey work is a significant suggestion. The alternative for distilled water is the tap, well or pump water available at site. The water from any of the latter sources is expected to contain dissolved salts the composition of which will vary from place to place. In order to throw some light on the effect of the salts dissolved in water other than distilled water, a number of samples of water containing NaCl , Na_2SO_4 , Na_2CO_3 , NaHCO_3 , and $\text{Ca}(\text{HCO}_3)_2$ in varying proportions were artificially prepared by dissolving the salts in distilled water. The proportion of these salts in different types of waters is given in Table II.

TABLE II.

The proportion of various salts in 100 litres of the artificially prepared waters.

No.	Na ₂ CO ₃ .	NaHCO ₃ .	NaCl.	Na ₂ SO ₄ .	Ca(HCO ₃) ₂ .	Conductivity of water sample.
1	5	10	10	10	15	475
2	—	—	10	10	30	510
3	—	25	10	15	—	550
4	5	15	—	—	30	345
5	—	—	25	25	—	675

It is apparent from the above table that although the total amount of the salts dissolved in the various samples of water is the same still their conductivities are fairly different. The water samples containing NaCl and Na₂SO₄ have the maximum conductivity, while those containing carbonate and bicarbonates have the minimum. The rest have intermediate values of conductivities. Table IV gives the conductivities of the soil suspensions in the above artificially prepared water samples and distilled water—the latter for the sake of comparison. If there is no interaction between the soil and the salts dissolved in water then the following relation should hold good :

$$\begin{array}{l} \text{Conductivity of soil sus-} \\ \text{pension in the salt-} \\ \text{containing water} \\ (A) \end{array} = \begin{array}{l} \text{conductivity of soil} \\ \text{suspension in} \\ \text{distilled water} \\ (B) \end{array} + \begin{array}{l} \text{conductivity of the} \\ \text{salt-containing} \\ \text{water.} \\ (C) \end{array}$$

(A) was, however, invariably found less than the sum of B and C, i.e., a marked depression of conductivity occurred by making the suspension of soil in the salt-containing waters. The depression was found to increase with increase in salt content of soils and varied with different water samples in the following way :—

(i) Minimum depression occurred in water samples containing preponderating amounts of NaCl and Na₂SO₄.

(ii) Maximum depression occurred in water samples containing more calcium and sodium bicarbonates. In one case, i.e., soil No. 2672 the depression is even more than the conductivity of that soil in distilled water.

(iii) In general the ratio of the conductivity of soil in distilled water to the depression caused by using salt water for making soil suspension instead increases with an increase in the salt content of soils.

From the above it is obvious that the use of waters, other than distilled, produces certain complications on account of the interaction of the salts dissolved in water and the salts associated with soils or the bases in

TABLE III.

Conductivities of soil suspensions in artificially prepared water samples.

Sr. No.	Reg No. of soil	Conductivities of soil suspension in					
		Distilled water.	Artificial water No. 1.*	Artificial water No. 2.*	Artificial water No. 3.*	Artificial water No. 4.*	Artificial water No. 5.*
	Without soil	—	475	510	550	345	675
1	2672	110	500 (85)**	520 (100)**	580 (80)**	340 (115)**	705 (80)**
2	6068	120	500 (95)	560 (70)	550 (120)	400 (65)	740 (55)
3	260	130	540 (65)	560 (80)	600 (80)	360 (115)	750 (55)
4	6066	140	525 (90)	545 (105)	620 (70)	375 (170)	730 (65)
5	247 ^a	140	540 (75)	575 (75)	640 (50)	375 (120)	775 (40)
6	2443	320	690 (105)	750 (80)	560 (320)	350 (315)	925 (70)
7	3019	570	890 (155)	980 (100)	990 (130)	680 (235)	1120 (125)
8	2477	720	1050 (135)	1060 (160)	1120 (140)	880 (175)	1220 (165)
9	2413	830	1200 (105)	1200 (140)	1340 (30)	1050 (125)	1400 (105)
10	3159	850	1200 (125)	1150 (210)	1260 (140)	1010 (185)	1400 (125)

* The composition of the salts dissolved in these waters is given in Table II

** The figures in brackets indicate the depression, *i.e.*, the difference between B + C and A (*vide supra*).

the exchange complex of soils which affected the conductivities of soil suspensions. Distilled water must therefore be exclusively used for this type of work..

The Use of Conductometric Method of Determining Soluble Salt Content to Soil from Different parts of India

To test this method the soluble salt content of a set of soils obtained from different parts of India was determined conductometrically from their 1 : 15 soil suspensions. The results are given in Table IV and show a fair agreement with the values of soluble salt content determined gravimetrically from soil extracts. It seems, therefore, justifiable that this quick method of determining soluble salt content may usefully be adopted throughout the country for soil survey work.

TABLE IV.

No.	Description of the sample.	Soluble salt content (direct).	Salt content derived from conductivity of 1 : 25 soil suspensions.
1	Surface soil, a composite sample from different estate soils, Coimbatore	0.04%	0.05%
2	Soil sample from Agricultural Farm, Block D surface foot, Tarnab, N.W.F.P.	0.096	0.08
3	Sir Ganga Soil (Punjab).	0.11	0.11
4	Surface soil sample, top 8 inches, Khat Taluk, Malabar... ..	0.08	0.11
5	Soil sample from Agricultural Farm, Block BP, Tarnab, N.W.F.P.	0.10	0.13
6	Soil sample from Raghobpur District, Etawah, U. P.	0.09	0.13
7	Surface soil sample from Irrigated cotton field (F. No. 4) Cotton Breeding Station, Coimbatore	0.11	0.16
8	Soil sample from plot used for growing kidney beans, Agricultural College Farm, Lyallpur, Punjab.	0.18	0.16
9	Bara soil 91/D/4. Punjab.	0.14	0.20
10	Soil sample from Pot Culture House, Shillong.	0.21	0.26
11	Soil sample from Toclai Experimental Station, Zorbheta.	0.26	0.27
12	Soil sample from Pot Culture House, Kalvanpur.	0.296	0.23
13	Soil sample from Pot Culture House, Akola.	0.33	0.30
14	Soil sample from Maviya, Khara and Kalli District, Lucknow, U. P.	0.392	0.35
15	Soil sample from treated (1 west) plot, Sakrand, Sind.	0.838	1.10
16	Soil sample from untreated plot A/2C2, Sakrand, Sind	1.328	1.55
17	Alkali soil sample from Travancore.	1.49	1.70
18.	Soil sample from Gursikran (Usar), District Aligarh, U.P..	1.746	1.75
19	Soil sample from Lakhanpur and Kainjari (Usar tract) Tehsil Auraiya District, Etawah, U.P.	1.692	1.80

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IRRIGATION RESEARCH INSTITUTE,
LAHORE.

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